

The Need for Measuring Creativity and Specific Methods for Measure It

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Annotation. This article describes the theoretical description of creativity, the need for measure it and how creativity can be measured. The specific measurements tests are offered by researchers based on the studies.

Keywords: creativity, divergent thinking tests, elaboration, consensual assessment technique, self-report, innovation

Introduction

Creativity is an important component of our capacity to set innovations. Creativity is thinking up new things, innovation is doing new things (Theodore Levitt). Through these innovations, individuals and organizations can keep up with the latest trends and technological advancements in their industrial path, which is emerging as the most crucial factor to impact business success in today's dynamic and competitive environment. In this paper, I will outline theoretical descriptions of creativity and innovation, the need for specific measurements of them and how they can be measured.

Theoretical Description of Creativity and Innovation

In Ancient Greece, the term innovation emerged from the concept (kainotomia) and had a political meaning (Cropley, 2000). This political connotation survived over time, and made its entry into another vocabulary - Latin, with its positive meaning. Christian writers and poets used this word as "in-nova", which means renewing, rebirth, regeneration and reformation. From that time on, this term became a catchword that everyone understood, referring to any new advancement and initiative. Regarding historical roots of Creativity, there is no single universally accepted theoretical description. However, multiple perspectives and theories can give broader descriptions. Creativity shaped by social involvement, shared knowledge and cultural standards and norms. Creativity has often been 'observed' inside people and their particular attempts. It started from the Renaissance and its emphasis on 'great creators', keeping on with the late eighteenth and nineteenth century 'elevation of the individual self' (Glaveanu, 2010). One of the most recent historical era that generated our perception of creativity was Enlightenment. This period shaped an intellectual movement that dominated in Europe in the eighteenth century (Glaveanu, 2018). Then, the Industrial Revolution accepted the transformation of creativity through the utilization of new technological innovations. Science and Innovations became the drivers of this progress, and new forms of creativity started to be implemented and valued. Creativity was the thing which addressed practical and technical issues to build better societies.

The Need for Specific Measurements of Creativity and Innovation.

Why should creativity be measured? This question made a lot of researchers delve into finding arguments to it. If we desire to enhance creativity, we need to measure it. Without using adequate tools to measure, there is no other way to define that the policies in place are being effective. There is no single area or sphere that does not require divergent thinking.

Historically, various methods and intelligence checking tests were utilized to define people's creativity level. However, these types of conventional indicators require convergent thinking which has to give correct answers to standardized tests (Lubart, 2016). Nowadays, social and environmental factors seem to play a pivotal role in creative performance, particularly in

organizational settings. Thus, most organizations check creativity level of employees in addition to specific intelligence and experiences related to the chosen working area. To provide these needs, it is required to generate a particular assessment system for Human Resource for the process of hiring employees. These innovation level metrics help employers to make up their minds in terms of employee promotions and rewards (Goffin and Mitchell, 2010). There are needs for special measures of creativity and innovation level to assess its current status in order to learn shortages and anticipate its potential future.

How can Creativity be measured?

Measuring creativity and innovation is a complex process, as they are multifaceted concepts influenced by social, individual and environmental factors. At regional and national levels, it is difficult to find indicators that say more about the creative capacity of a country than the educational attainment of a population. Researchers have improved diverse methods and approaches to assess creativity, emphasizing on various aspects including divergent thinking and creative achievement. The following are some of the most widely used methods:

1) Divergent Thinking Tests

Divergent thinking is the capability where an individual generates multiple answers and solutions to an issue. It is mostly considered an essential part of creativity. The TTCT (Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking) is an example of widely used tools for assessing divergent thinking. It measures fluency (number of ideas), originality (uniqueness of an idea), flexibility (diversity of ideas), and elaboration (details of ideas) (Torrance, 1966). These tests focus on measuring ability to analyse various possibilities. TTCT tests are used in business and education to measure capacity of individuals for creativity. Torrance (1966) wrote that showing good results in TTCT tests does not guarantee an individual's creativity abilities. Thus, the purposes of these tests are for exploration, research and for general use, along with defining potential strengths of learners. Although they primarily assess divergent thinking, there are some limitations with them, which neglects other components including originality and problem-solving. Moreover, test-taking skills may impact them and may not always connect with creative behavior in real-world situations.

2) Creative Achievement Questionnaires (CAQ)

The CAQ measures creative accomplishments of an individual in different real-world domains: science, visual arts, music, dance, architectural design, creative writing, humor, scientific discovery, theater/film, and culinary. These tests are reported to be as a reliable method of measuring creativity (Carson, 2005). The CAQ has items which cover various levels of achievement, from beginner to professional recognition, scored on a 0-7 scale. It is used to study the relationship of creativity with personal traits such as empathy and openness. The CAQ is a vigorous tool for assessing creative achievement, with powerful practical support for its test-retest reliability and validity that predicts real-world creative success. However, it has certain criticisms and limitations related to self-report bias and cultural specificity, making individuals overestimate their achievements.

3) Consensual Assessment Technique (CAT)

The CAT includes using experts in a given sphere to measure the creativity of a product (e.g., artwork, or a sculpture) independently. This approach utilizes the idea that creativity is best judged by those familiar with the domain (Amabile, 1982). Focusing on the social and psychological aspects of creativity, experts often judge novelty and value within a certain domain. However, it has a number of limitations related to the subjective expertise of raters that can lead to biases.

4) Self-report Scales

These questionnaires ask individuals about their own creative personal traits and behaviors. Self-report scales evaluate a person's self-recognition of own creative abilities and potentials (Runco, 2014). These measurements provide comprehensive qualitative database and capture the dynamic nature of creative processes. However, social and personal biases may not accurately represent actual creative performance (Amabile, 1996). Most experts find it difficult to evaluate findings and consider it as a time-consuming process.

Conclusion

It is important to state that measuring creativity is an ongoing sphere of research, and a perfect measurement tool has not been detected yet.

The choice of method is determined by exploring research question and the type of participants (organization or individual). For instance, an individual's creative potential can be assessed by divergent thinking tests, while the CAT measures are more suitable for assessing organizational performance. Multiple approaches are often combined to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of creativity and innovation with quantitative and qualitative data. Understanding these various measurement methods let us study more effective and support the improvement of creativity across diverse domains.

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